

GREEN DIGITAL BUSINESS CAPABILITY AS DETERMINANT FACTORS TO SUSTAIN FIRM PERFORMANCE. MARKET BASED MODEL INNOVATION ADDRESSES AS MEDIATED VARIABLE. A STUDY FROM THE PERFECTIVENESS OF DYNAMIC CAPABILITY THEORY

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Abstract

Digitalization has shaped the new business paradigm, and integration of various digitalization factors is inevitable for industries to reach performance sustainability. This research aims to investigate how various digitalization factors trigger industrial performance sustainability. Based on dynamic capability, this research focuses on the analysis of the relationship between exogenous (digital exploitation capabilities, digital exploration capabilities, digitalization strategy adoption, digital transformation, and digital infrastructure capabilities) and endogenous variables (sustainable business performance). Moreover, this study also investigates the mediating role of market-driven business model innovation and customized business model innovation. This research is the first study that explores the mechanism of the intervening variable between market-based business innovation and digital leadership capability. The findings of this model are relevant to guide the industries in current digital economics by innovating to obtain sustainable business performance. The survey was used as the data collection method by distributing questionnaires to the managers through Google Forms to the official email. 500 questionnaires were distributed, and 388 were valid for further data analysis, with a 77,6% response rate. The questionnaires were divided into two sections. The first section is dedicated to demographic information, and the second section is focused on research model variables such as Digital Exploitation Capabilities (DEC), Digital Exploration Capabilities (DEC), Digitalization Strategy Adoption (DSA, Digital Transformation (DT), Digital Infrastructure Capabilities (DIC), intervening variables such as Market-Driven Business Model Innovation (MDBMI) and Customized Business Model Innovation (CBMI). All proposed hypotheses are accepted.

Keywords: Digital Exploration Capabilities, Digitalization Strategy Adoption, Digital Transformation, Digital Infrastructure Capabilities, Market-Driven Business Model Innovation, Customized Business Model Innovation.

INTRODUCTION

The evolving business landscape has underscored the critical role of innovation in companies' adaptation to emerging developments (AlNuaimi et al., 2022; Shehzad et al., 2021). The recent digital expansion has disrupted traditional markets, introducing new challenges for global industries.

According to Brenner and Hartl (Brenner & Hartl, 2021), industries often navigate this volatile environment without the necessities, capabilities, and coherent digital strategies, making it difficult to achieve sustained performance, which has become a significant challenge for many sectors (Sarfraz et al., 2022). Therefore, this study aims to inspire industries to transform digitally to ensure sustainable business performance.

Aligned with the rapid growth of businesses, digital transformation has emerged as an essential tool to acquire sustainable success (Broccardo et al., 2023). According to Busulwa (Busulwa et al., 2020), digital transformation gives enterprises new capacities and infrastructures, these aspects will improve their long-term performance. By utilizing and investigating technical frameworks, industries must implement suitable methods of Ambidexterity Digital (AD) to reduce market volatility. The ability of a company to integrate new technology and reorganize current business processes is known as digital exploitation capability, or DEC (March, 1991).

This capability can assist industries in pursuing sustainable performance by refining current practices, including skills, knowledge, and information technology applications (Belhadi et al., 2022). Information technology and communication are vital antecedents in enabling industries to enhance their capabilities and maintain performance standards (Wang et al., 2023). Over the past decade, integrating exploitation and exploration capabilities in the digital realm has gained significance for long-term business sustainability.

According to Levinthal and March (Levinthal, 1993), the ability of a firm to adopt new models, resources, and knowledge to improve industrial processes is digital exploration capability (DEC), a proactive strategy that encourages industries to adopt innovative practices that are crucial to sustainable performance (Jacobs & Maritz, 2020) and business model innovation (Tariq et al., 2022)

In contemporary times, emerging technologies are employed to address evolving market dynamics. (Mikalef et al., 2020) noted that the expansion of digital opportunities has fostered the development of businesses and cultivated a data-driven culture to respond the market demands. One of the primary strategies for adapting to market fluctuations is to leverage these new opportunities, which allow firms to pursue innovation (Sun et al., 2021).

Business Model Innovation (BMI) is influenced by market conditions, stemming from adaptive development that alters business assessments and enables industries to meet market demands (Herhausen, 2016). Designing and overseeing innovation processes that address the demands of prospective clients is a component of market-driven BMI (Codini et al., 2023). This strategy makes it easier for industries to allocate resources in a way that best meets the needs of their target market (Lima et al., 2023). In particular, market-driven BMI is a long-term improvement of industry innovation processes.

Industries are adaptive to a dynamic business environment (Hanlin, 2023). This adaptability is fundamentally linked to the initial development of customer value co-creation. Technology integration through digital transformation brings advantageous points to the stakeholders, by creating an effective digitalization strategy (Porfírio et al., 2021). In consequence, industries must improve their performance sustainability (Borah et al., 2022) at all operational levels. Nowadays, attaining sustainable performance requires a more strategic approach to meet stakeholder needs.

Due to its association with enhanced innovation potential and sustainable performance, the emphasis on digitalization initiatives has attracted a lot of attention (Bendig et al., 2023). Digital leadership is pivotal in the execution of strategic planning, as it facilitates the

identification of customer needs through the application of effective and efficient digital technologies (De Waal et al., 2016). Furthermore, digital leadership assists industries in assessing their market portfolios to drive business innovation and enhance sustainable performance (Benitez et al., 2022). In the contemporary business landscape, digital leadership establishes a foundational platform for digital transformation, thereby enabling the realization of sustainable performance benefits (Türk, 2023).

Consequently, digital leadership capability (DLC) pertains to the environmental conditions necessary for digital transformation and encompasses the ability to guide business innovation through digital tools (Turyadi et al., 2023). By encompassing skills and profound digital competencies, such as digital literacy, strategic thinking, and flexibility, DLC enables industries to leverage innovation.

Hence, DLC reflects leaders' understanding of how technology is important for decision-making, business modeling, and increasing industry agility (Tigre et al., 2023). Bacca-Acosta (Bacca-Acosta et al., 2023) highlighted that the technology possesses greater breadth and flexibility compared to its predecessors. A notable limitation identified in the research is that contemporary organizations have adopted current advancements to enhance sustainability within their industries (Raj et al., 2020; SARFRAZ et al., 2022). The present study aims to bridge this gap by examining various factors of digitalization that contribute to fostering sustainable performance in industries.

This study examines the relationship between exogenous factors (like digital exploitation, exploration, adoption, transformation, and infrastructure capabilities), intervening factors (like market-driven and customized business model innovation), and endogenous factors (sustainable business performance) using the dynamic capability framework. Furthermore, this study explores the influence of intervening business models driven by market forces and the impact of digital leadership on the relationship with sustainable performance.

A new perspective on digitalization has been developed, as outlined in this study, which presents innovative ideas related to topics that warrant scientific inquiry. In response to the evolving business landscape, the insufficient understanding of digital transformation underscores the significance of robust IT initiatives in ensuring the sustainable performance of industries (Annarelli et al., 2021).

The significance of technology innovation and digitization has been studied in the past, to help industries meet the needs of marketers, broader research is crucial. Based on the literature exploration, this is the first study to look at the function of the intervening variable between digital leadership capability and market-driven business model innovation (Bhatta et al., 2023; Zhang et al., 2023).

This model is applicable in the present digital economy since its findings support businesses in their pursuit of innovation and sustainable performance by providing relevant insights for academics, practitioners, policymakers, and global industries. In accordance, we advised the urgency for the management to reevaluate their resources and improve their digital competencies in light of the benefits of digitalization to achieve sustainable corporate

performance. The results of the fundamental ideas of digital innovation and transformation are valuable resources that support conversations on long-term stability. In conclusion, this study urges sectors to employ the acquired knowledge and nurture an atmosphere that highlights the significance of skills and digital components in attaining long-term success.

LITERATURE REVIEWS AND HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

Theory of Dynamic Capability (TDC)

The foundation of capability theory concerning dynamic resources emphasizes the importance of investigating how industries have evolved and adapted their capabilities to attain sustainability. The ability of the company to absorb, grow, and reorganize both internal and external skills in response to swift changes in the environment is known as TDC, and it is incorporated into this study (Teece et al., 1997).

TDC can facilitate strategic transformations in business functions, enabling the firm to achieve sustainable performance. Given the distinctiveness of the current conceptual model, understanding the elements within this theory can assist firms in optimizing their resources, thereby fostering business innovation and enhancing overall innovation capacity. Industries must expand and enhance their digital capabilities to satisfy customer demands for innovation, which is recognized as a fundamental requirement for contemporary industries. Fostering innovation requires industries to develop their resources, capabilities, expertise, and exclusive technologies (Hutton et al., 2021). Digital capabilities in industries are a crucial engine of innovation and long-term performance, and they must be further enhanced to react to changing market needs.

This theory is well-suited for analyzing the precursors of digital transformation, business model innovation to market dynamics, and ambidextrous capabilities. For many years, the capabilities of exploration and exploitation have garnered significant attention. As indicated in the TDC, industries must identify their business assets and seize innovation opportunities (van Lieshout et al., 2021). This theory facilitates a direct understanding of ambidexterity and encourages an examination of both exploitation and exploration capabilities, particularly in the context of innovation. Overall, the digital factors examined through this theoretical lens can elucidate the connections among digital strategy adoption, digital transformation, business model innovation supported by market conditions, and sustainable performance. These elements empower industries to realign their resources in response to market demands.

Digital Exploitation Capabilities

Digital technologies like block chain, artificial intelligence, and big data have been increasingly popular during the last ten years.(Yadav et al., 2023). Experts across various fields have transformed industry operations. Unforeseen and dynamic changes have prompted industries to leverage new digital tools, creating business opportunities. To capitalize on the potential of Digital Technology (DT), industries must effectively utilize and develop their resources (Hussain et al., 2021). By optimizing firm resources through technology, organizations can enhance sustainability.

This approach enables industries to reassess their digital strategies, ultimately improving efficiency and business processes, leading to sustainable performance (Wang et al., 2023). The efficiency of industries is contingent upon advancements in management practices facilitated by technological innovations (Gupta et al., 2023). These capabilities empower organizations to utilize digital resources as primary drivers of sustainable performance.

The introduction of new technology, which alters existing organizational operational methods, has prompted industries to reassess their current models and procedures (Singh & Kumar, 2020). Industries need to recognize prevailing market demands and implement new technologies to create more agile systems. Industries have adopted Digital Enterprise Capabilities (DEC) to address existing market needs (Tariq et al., 2022). The DEC of firms has enabled industries to adjust to market fluctuations, allowing them to respond swiftly to market requirements by utilizing more efficient digital resources (Bresciani et al., 2021).

This has fundamentally transformed the structures, processes, services, and operational procedures within industries. Hossain et al. (Hossain et al., 2023) asserted that digital innovation within industries aligns their capabilities with market demands. Consequently, based on the Digital Transformation Concept (DTC), the reviewed literature indicates that DEC enhances adaptive capabilities and fosters innovation, which can lead to increased sustainability and the evolution of business models driven by market dynamics (Gupta et al., 2023). In light of these findings, the following hypotheses are proposed:

H1(a) Digital Exploitation Capability (DEC) is designed to have advantages effect on Sustainable Business Performance (SBP)

H1(b). Digital exploitation capability (DEC) is designed to have advantages effect on market-driven business model innovation.

H1(c). Digital exploitation capability (DEC) is designed to have advantages effect on Customized Business Model Innovation (CMBI)

Digital Exploration Capabilities (DEC)

Over the past ten years, DEC has become an essential aspect to response the globalization complexity. The magnitude of today's global issues has led to several problems, such as the depletion of resources and the need for creative solutions. To provide a comprehensive understanding, DEC led to the use of new technologies (Moreira et al., 2022). DEC continues to advance research, innovation, and technology adoption to foster sustainable growth and boost industrial value for customers (Zhang et al., 2023).

This approach enables industries to optimize their business functions through the acquisition of knowledge and new skills (Permatasari et al., 2023). Furthermore, it allows industries to leverage technology to improve sustainable business performance. The advancement of sophisticated technologies that transform business operations supports industries in achieving sustainable outcomes (Arshad et al., 2022). In contemporary times, digital exploration activities represent the most effective means of enhancing sustainability.

According to Belhadi et al. (Belhadi et al., 2022), dynamic capabilities (DC) enable industries to take advantage of new market opportunities by utilizing a variety of perspectives, ideas, and information, which improves long-term performance. Recognizing changes in the market has spurred industries to adapt quickly by increasing their research and revenue sources (Shpak et al., 2023). (Kagan et al., 2021) indicated that entrepreneurial capabilities (EC) assist industries in comprehending the evolving needs and demands of the market. EC encourages the enhancement of existing technical capabilities. Economic activities also drive industries to adopt new processes to meet market demands (Zhang et al., 2023). This aligns to address market needs through new technologies (K. Liu, 2023). Existing literature indicates that DC mechanisms generate new value for customers, providing innovative opportunities for industries to achieve superior performance in response to market demands (Tariq et al., 2022). These insights have led to the formulation of the following hypotheses:

H2(a). Digital exploration capability (DEC) is designed to have advantages effect on Market-Driven Business Model Innovation (MDBMI)

H2(b). Digital exploration capability (DEC) is designed to have an advantageous effect on Sustainable Business Performance (SBP).

H2(c). Digital exploration capability (DEC) is designed to have advantages in Customized Business Model Innovation (CMBI)

Digitalization Strategy Adoption (DSA)

Industries that have undergone significant transformations have developed new strategies to ensure ongoing sustainability. Over the past decade, the adoption of digital strategies has become essential to sustainability efforts. Digitalization has enabled industries to leverage new technologies, facilitating the creation of digital strategies that enhance operational management activities. Digital strategies encompass the ability to transform, develop skills, and optimize business processes at all levels, thereby allowing firms to maintain their performance (Feroz et al., 2021).

The potential of these strategies has prompted managers to utilize technology that ensures long-term performance for industries. Furthermore, digitalization has encouraged industries to innovate their traditional strategies through sustainable innovations (S. Liu et al., 2023). The integration of digital strategies has streamlined transformative processes, guiding industries toward achieving sustainable performance (Li et al., 2022).

In contemporary times, the technological capabilities of industries have significantly contributed to the achievement of their objectives (Xu et al., 2023). (Ly, 2024) indicated that digital transformation (DT) enhances the agility of data science (DS) development, which in turn fosters sustainable business performance. Digital business strategies (DBS) that prioritize sustainable performance allow organizations to swiftly adapt to the rapid changes in dynamic markets (SARFRAZ et al., 2022). By leveraging the potential of digital tools, firms can capitalize on existing market opportunities.

The adoption of data science enables industries to sustain their adaptability in a vast and evolving environment (AlNuaimi et al., 2022). Canhoto et al. (Canhoto et al., 2021) demonstrated that the implementation of data science facilitates industries in modifying their functions to meet market demands. Data science is a creative solution that streamlines customer interactions and improves organizational effectiveness while matching client objectives. (Correani et al., 2020) justify the role of data science which serves as a road map for guiding creative activities, enabling companies to leverage digital transformation to add value for prospective clients. Hence, the following hypotheses are proposed:

H3 (a). Digitalization Strategy Adoption (DSA) is designed to have an advantageous effect on Market-Driven Business Model Innovation (MDBMI).

H3(b). Digitalization Strategy Adoption (DSA) is designed to have an advantageous effect on Sustainable Business Performance (SBP).

H3 (c). Digitalization Strategy Adoption (DSA) is designed to have advantages effect on Customized Business Model Innovation (CMBI)

Digital Transformation Advantages (DTA)

Every company strives for long-term success. This situation is due to the triple bottom-line paradigm, which emphasizes the importance of implementing digital transformation (Xu et al., 2023). Companies are responsible for ensuring that their operations prioritize health and social security. In this context, digital transformation is crucial to significantly contribute to the new economy (Sarfraz et al., 2022). Various industries are experiencing continuous growth due to advances in information technology (Chygryn & Shevchenko, 2023). Digital transformation activities have emerged as key determinants for industrial growth.

This transformation fosters innovation and sustainable changes in business models, ultimately enhancing sustainability performance (SARFRAZ et al., 2022). The effective utilization of digital resources boosts business productivity, thereby improving production, services, and overall sustainable performance (Costa Melo et al., 2023). Leveraging technical resources through digital transformation serves as a fundamental strategy to enhance the sustainability of industries (Ahmad et al., 2021). By implementing this approach, industries can streamline operations, procedures, and capabilities, leading to improved outcomes (Martínez-Peláez et al., 2023).

Currently, the emergence of new technologies and data-centric approaches are driving the early stages of the innovation process. Digital transformation (DT) has provided numerous opportunities for companies to improve their technical skills, knowledge, and capabilities to meet customer demands (Skare et al., 2023). DT has created greater avenues for businesses to maintain sustainability and foster innovation. It serves as a sophisticated instrument that assists industries in reaching their innovative objectives.

(Chang et al., 2020) demonstrated how digital transformation (DT) enhances technological skills and organizational transparency, supporting industrial business models. DT encourages creativity and enables businesses to react swiftly to changes in the market. In the face of

technical advancements, it symbolizes the industry's capacity to reorganize organizational elements, practices, culture, and strategies in order to satisfy market needs (Pramanik et al., 2019). According to (Wang et al., 2023), DT simplifies business operations to predict market demand and increase value co-creation with customers. (Olsson & Bosch, 2020) illustrated that DT bolsters the Business Innovation Model (BIM), enabling proactive value creation for customers and guiding the adoption of disruptive technologies. Consequently, existing literature indicates that numerous innovative digital solutions have influenced market dynamics, leading many industries to embrace BIM-based approaches to satisfy customer needs (Cappiello, 2020). This supports the subsequent hypotheses.

H4(a). Digital Transformation (DT) is designed to have an advantageous effect on Market-Driven Business Model Innovation (MDBMI).

H4(b). Digital Transformation (DT) is designed to have an advantageous effect on Sustainable Business Performance (SBP).

H4(c). Digital Transformation (DT) is designed to have advantages effect on Customized Business Model Innovation (CMBI)

Digital Infrastructure Capability (DIC)

Digital Infrastructure Capability (DIC) refers to the ability of an industry to effectively manage and utilize digital infrastructure, including information technology, networking, and data, to enhance business strategy, foster innovation, and improve operations. This concept encompasses technological resources, human expertise, and supporting processes. Bharadwaj et al. (2013) characterized DIC as the industry's capacity to strategically integrate and leverage digital technologies, while Sambamurthy, Bharadwaj, and Grover (2003) highlighted the significance of DIC in establishing a competitive advantage through technology.

Key components of DIC include digital technologies such as cloud computing, which enhances flexibility and operational efficiency (Marston et al., 2011), Big Data Analytics (BDA), which provides strategic insights from large datasets (Chen, Chiang, & Storey, 2012), and the Internet of Things (IoT), which connects physical tools to digital systems to form an integrated ecosystem (Borgia, 2014). Additionally, industry competency encompasses IT governance, which regulates technology use (Weill & Ross, 2004), and agility, which pertains to the ability to swiftly adapt to technological changes (Teece, Pisano, & Shuen, 1997). Finally, collaboration within the digital ecosystem fosters partnerships among organizations to enhance digital capabilities (Tanriverdi, Rai, & Venkatraman, 2010).

Significant theoretical frameworks underpin Digital Innovation Capability (DIC), including the **Resource-Based View (RBV)**. According to Barney (1991), DIC can be regarded as strategic resources that possess value, rarity, inimitability, and lack substitutes. Additionally, **the Dynamic Capability Framework**, as articulated by Teece, Pisano, and Shuen (1997), emphasizes that the ability to integrate, develop, and reconfigure technological competencies is essential for adapting to rapid changes in the digital landscape.

Furthermore, the **Socio-Technical Systems Theory**, proposed by Trist (1981), highlights that the advancement of DIC necessitates a synergistic relationship between digital technology and human elements within an organization. Previous research on business performance indicates several key findings. Bharadwaj et al. (2013) noted that Digital Infrastructure Capability (DIC) can enhance operational efficiency and improve customer satisfaction.

Similarly, Mithas et al. (2011) found a correlation between investments in DIC and an increase in financial performance within industries. Regarding innovation, Yoo, Boland, and Lyytinen (2012) highlighted that DIC allows industries to create modular innovations and supports rapid experimentation.

However, challenges in DIC development persist. Kohli and Grover (2008) identified organizational resistance to change, a deficiency in digital skills, and outdated technological infrastructure as significant obstacles. Looking ahead, discussions are likely to focus on the integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning, as noted by Brynjolfsson and McAfee (2017), since AI enhances the ability to predict digital infrastructure needs and streamline processes.

Additionally, the trend towards Sustainability and Green IT, as discussed by Murugesan (2008), shows that organizations are beginning to adopt green technologies to improve energy efficiency. Furthermore, the implementation of Blockchain and Edge Computing, as described by Iansiti and Lakhani (2017), promises better decentralization and enhanced data security within digital infrastructures. Based on these findings, the following hypotheses are proposed.

H5(a). Digital Infrastructure Capability (DIC) is designed to have an advantageous effect on Market-Driven Business Model Innovation (MDBMI).

H5(a). Digital Infrastructure Capability (DIC) is designed to have an advantageous effect on Sustainable Business Performance (SBP).

H5(a). Digital Infrastructure Capability (DIC) is designed to have advantages in Customized Business Model Innovation (CMBI)

Market-Driven Business Model Innovation (MDBMI)

In recent years, digitalization has resulted in fast alterations of business models and structures (Zhou et al., 2021) in response to shifting client expectations. As market transparency has increased, customer preferences have also shifted. This evolution has compelled industries to swiftly adapt to environmental changes while maintaining sustainable performance (Sun et al., 2021). Customer demand plays a pivotal role in digitalization, positioning industries as catalysts for sustainable business innovation (Weidner et al., 2021). Market-driven Building Information Modeling (BIM) has emerged as a new avenue for enhancing revenue and business value.

A market-oriented innovation paradigm has aided digital transformation, requiring sectors to acquire new essential skills, capabilities, and knowledge (Schlegel & Kraus, 2023) for sustainability. As a result of this application, industries can achieve long-term success by reinventing their functions and current processes (Alerasoul et al., 2022).

Industries have skillfully responded to their customers' ultimate needs. The business model utilized by market-driven industries significantly adapts to customer needs through technology, thereby achieving sustainable performance (Mai et al., 2021). Digital technology has accelerated the business innovation process in this dynamic era, evolving into a key factor for enhancing sustainable performance. Consequently, the following hypotheses are put forward:

H5. Market-Driven Business Model Innovation is Designed to Have Advantages Effect on Sustainable Business Performance (SBP).

Customized Business Model Innovation (CBMI)

Significant disruption and a change in leadership dynamics that emerged from digital transformation have emphasized innovation and market demands (Jagadisen et al., 2022). Digital transformation has assessed company services and procedures that leverage digital technologies across a range of industries over time.

The advancement of digital transformation keeps enhancing digital competencies, particularly leadership, which is essential for satisfying customer wants (Sarfraz et al., 2023). Maintaining long-term success and standardizing IT infrastructure depends heavily on digital leadership (Shin et al., 2023). This approach will enhance IT proficiency in fields needed to meet the growing demand for digital goods.

Digital transformation has recently drawn the attention of industries to shifts in market demand and innovation. This has become a crucial part of understanding customer portfolios. Market-driven business innovation has ensured that critical features of management and technology integration for long-term performance (Mollah et al., 2023).

Rapid changes have made the interaction between digital leadership and technology a crucial topic in academic literature (Karakose & Tülübaş, 2023). Buyukbese et al. (Büyükebeşe et al., 2022) found that digital leadership makes the best use of technology to achieve long-term performance (Sağbaşı & Erdoğan, 2022). Digital leaders have been found to have a significant impact on the long-term performance of industries. In the field of digitalization, where digital transformation has created a new paradigm, digital leadership has effectively responded to customer needs (Y. Liu, 2022).

Digital leadership has compelled industries to standardize their infrastructural integration, procedures, and IT frameworks in alignment with market demands. This necessity has driven industries to implement changes in business processes, skills, and management practices, thereby achieving sustainable business performance (Ryan Bula et al., 2023). Ultimately, the capability of digital leadership represents the integration of various industries, characterized by agility in the evolving business landscape (Chatterjee et al., 2023). Consequently, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H6. Customized Business Model Innovation (CBMI) is Designed to Have Advantages Effect on Sustainable Business Performance (SBP).

To summarize, the following Grand Theoretical Model (GTM).

Fig 1: Theoretical framework

Source: Literatures Review (2025)

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This survey targeted managers. The data was collected by conducting an online survey by disseminating questionnaires via Google Forms to the official email addresses. At the early stage, 500 questionnaires were distributed, and 388 were valid for subsequent data analysis. The response rate for the questionnaires was 77.6%.

To enhance the return rate, some respondents received reminders. The questionnaires were divided into two different sections. The first section gathered demographic information. The second section concentrated on the exogenous variables, including Digital Exploitation Capabilities (DEC), Digital Exploration Capabilities (DEC), Digitalization Strategy Adoption (DSA), Digital Transformation (DT), and Digital Infrastructure Capabilities (DIC).

This section also addressed intervening variables such as Market-Driven Business Model Innovation (MDBMI) and Customized Business Model Innovation (CBMI), culminating in the endogenous variable of Sustainable Business Performance (SBP).

Table 1 describes the respondents' characteristics. Most of the respondents are male, accounting for 65% of the total respondents, and 35% are female. The predominant age group is 31-40 years, accounting for 46% of the respondents. The majority of the respondents hold a bachelor's degree as their last education, representing 71% of total respondents. Regarding marital status, 77% of the respondents are single.

Most respondents have been working for their current companies for more than 15 years. Joint ventures constitute 36% of the company types. Related to the workforce, 54% of the companies ranged from 100 to 500 employees. The industrial and manufacturing sectors account for 65%, while the digital technology sector, specifically in IoT, comprises 40%. For further details, please refer to the following table.

Table 1: Demographic characteristics.

Items	Frequency (N = 388)	(%)
Gender		
• Male	256	0,65
• Female	132	0,35
Age		
• 21–30	88	0,22
• 31–40	180	0,46
• 41–50	85	0,22
• 51–60	35	0,09
Education		
• Bachelor	276	0,71
• Master	76	0,19
• MPhil	26	0,06
• Others	10	0,02
Marital Status		
• Single	296	0,77
• Married	92	0,23
Companies' basic information Age of the Company		
• 0–5 Years	74	0,19
• 6–10 Years	60	0,15
• 11–15 Years	120	0,30
• >15 Years	134	0,34
Nature of the Company		
• State-owned	76	0,19
• Private	132	0,34
• Joint Ventures	140	0,36
• Foreign investors	12	0,03
• Other	28	0,07
Company Size		
• Under 100 Employee	20	0,05
• 100-500 Employee	210	0,54
• 501-1000 Employee	100	0,25
• >1000 Employee	50	0,12
Company Type		
• IT services	10	0,02
• Industrial and manufacturing	256	0,65
• Consumer goods and retail	76	0,19
• Healthcare	34	0,08
• Others	12	0,03

Digital Technology		
• Big Data Analysis	4	0,01
• Databases	78	0,20
• Cloud Computing	94	0,24
• Artificial Intelligence	56	0,14
• Internet of Things	156	0,40

Source: Analyzed Data (2025)

Common Method Bias

Current research applied CMB by using the Harman-single factor approach. Extracted variance use factor 8,30 less than 50%, it showed that CMB is not found (Podsakoff et al., 2003).

RESULTS

Table 2 shows the statistical measurements of all study constructs. Each construct was assessed using different items, and all loading values reached 0.7, indicating high item reliability. The table also displays Cronbach's alpha, composite reliability (CR), and average variance extracted (AVE) for each construct. Further details can be found in Table 2.

Table 2: Reliability and validity analysis

Variables	Indicators	Loading	Alpha ≥ 0,70	CR ≥ 0,70	AVE ≥ 0,50
Digital Exploitation Capabilities (DEC)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technical Capabilities • Operational Proficiency • Organizational Capacity • Strategic Objectives and Outcomes 	0,81 0,80 0,87 0,80	0,826	0,75	0,68
Digital Exploration Capabilities (DEC)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technological Infrastructure • Innovation Ecosystem • Human Capital • Regulatory Environment • Strategic Alignment 	0,67 0,68 0,68 0,84 0,85	0,748	0,72	0,74
Digitalization Strategy Adoption (DSA)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strategic Alignment and Integration • Technological Infrastructure and Adoption • Human Capital and Skills Development • Process Transformation and Innovation • Customer and Stakeholder Engagement 	0,75 0,71 0,75 0,69 0,66	0,713	0,76	0,70
Digital Transformation (DT)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strategic Integration & Process Improvement • Technological Adoption • Emerging Technologies 	0,77 0,92 0,75	0,813	0,78	0,74
Market-Driven Business Model Innovation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Market Understanding • Innovation Processes • Customer Focus 	0,73 0,79 0,79	0,768	0,76	0,70

(MDBMI)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Financial Performance Organizational Capability 	0,76			
Customized Business Model Innovation (CBMI)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Customer Understanding Innovation Processes Customization Capabilities Customer Satisfaction and Loyalty Financial Performance 	0,58 0,64 0,77 0,83 0,68	0,752	0,79	74
Sustainable Business Performance (SBP)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Environmental Impact Social Responsibility Economic Performance Governance and Ethics Innovation and Improvement 	0,65 0,64 0,77 0,83 0,68	0,715	0,76	0,70

Source: Statistical Output (2025)

Table 3 displays the discriminant validity data for each construct employing the Heterotrait-Monotrait (HTMT) ratio and the Fornell-Larcker criterion. The Average Variance Extracted (AVE) adjusted r-squared is represented by the numbers along the diagonal. These diagonal values are important measures of discriminant validity; by the Fornell-Larcker method, they should be greater than the correlations shown by the off-diagonal values for other constructs. Further details are illustrated below.

Table 3: Discriminant Validity (Fornell Larcker & HTMT)

Constructs	(DT)	(DEC)	(DExC)	(DSA)	(MDBIM)	(CBMI)	(SBP)
Digital Transformation (DT)	0,864						
Digital Exploitation Capabilities (DEC)	0,079	0,741					
Digital Exploration Capabilities (DExC)	0,079	0,134	0,896				
Digitalization Strategy Adoption (DSA)	0,051	0,097	0,088	0,769			
Market Driven Business Model Innovation (MDBIM)	0,064	0,141	0,116	0,082	0,860		
Customized Business Model Innovation (CBMI)	0,071	0,081	0,125	0,088	0,069	0,702	
Sustainable Business Performance (SBP)	0,097	0,086	0,104	0,064	0,085	0,090	0,822

Note: “Values on the diagonal (italicized) represent the square root of the average variance extracted, while the off diagonals are correlation.”

The combination of the HTMT procedure with the Fornell-Larcker criteria provides a reliable way to evaluate discriminant validity in a research model. The full measured model is shown in the following figure.

Fig 2: Full Model Measurement

Table 4 presents the regression weights and illustrates the direct influence of each hypothesis. Hypothesis H1a posited that the Digital Exploitation Capability (DEC) is intended to positively affect Sustainable Business Performance (SBP), which was confirmed with a critical ratio (CR) of 1.993. Similarly, hypothesis H1b asserted that Digital Exploitation Capability (DEC) is aimed at positively influencing market-driven business model innovation, which was also validated with a CR of 6.162. However, hypothesis H1c remains to be addressed.

Digital exploitation capability (DEC) is intended to positively influence Customized Business Model Innovation (CMBI) with a CR value of 3,397. Hypothesis H2, which examines the role of Digital Exploration Capability (DEC) with Market-Driven Business Model Innovation (MDBMI), Sustainable Business Performance (SBP), and Customized Business Model Innovation (CMBI), has been validated with CR values of 2,300, 3,229, and 4,360, respectively.

The implementation of a digitalization strategy has been identified as a crucial precursor, with H3(a) indicating that the adoption of a Digitalization Strategy (DSA) positively influences Market-Driven Business Model Innovation (MDBMI), achieving a high critical ratio (CR) of 1.828, thus confirming H3(a). Conversely, H3(b), which posits that the Digitalization Strategy Adoption (DSA) positively impacts Sustainable Business Performance (SBP), was not supported, as it recorded a CR of 1.308. In contrast, H3(c) asserts that the Digitalization Strategy Adoption (DSA) has a beneficial effect on Customized Business Model Innovation (CMBI), which is accepted with a CR of 3.580.

The digital transformation was intended to provide benefits; however, it has proven to be inconsequential in influencing Customized Business Model Innovation (CMBI) and Market-Driven Business Model Innovation (MDBMI), as hypotheses H4a and H4c were rejected with CR values of 0.701 and 1.881, respectively. In contrast, hypothesis H4b, which posits that Digital Transformation (DT) has a beneficial impact on Sustainable Business Performance (SBP), was accepted with a CR of 5.841. Hypothesis H5, which suggested that Market-Driven Business Model Innovation is designed to positively affect Sustainable Business Performance (SBP), was rejected with a CR of 0.313. Finally, hypothesis H6, asserting that Customized Business Model Innovation (CBMI) is designed to have a positive effect on Sustainable Business Performance (SBP), was accepted with a CR of 4.006. For further information, please refer to Table 4.

Table 4: Regression Weights: (Group number 1 - Default model)

Hypotheses			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Label
Sustainable Business Performance	<---	Digital Exploitation Capabilities	,099	,050	1,993	,046	H1a
Market-Driven Business Model Innovation	<---	Digital Exploitation Capabilities	,451	,073	6,162	***	H1b
Customized Business Model Innovation	<---	Digital Exploration Capabilities	,205	,060	3,397	***	H1c
Market-Driven Business Model Innovation	<---	Digital Exploration Capabilities	,134	,058	2,300	,021	H2a
Sustainable Business Performance	<---	Digital Exploration Capabilities	,130	,040	3,229	,001	H2b
Customized Business Model Innovation	<---	Digital Exploration Capabilities	,227	,052	4,360	***	H2c
Market-Driven Business Model Innovation	<---	Digitalization Strategy Adoption	,142	,078	1,828	,068	H3a
Sustainable Business Performance	<---	Digitalization Strategy Adoption	,068	,052	1,308	,191	H3b
Customized Business Model Innovation	<---	Digitalization Strategy Adoption	,250	,070	3,580	***	H3c

Hypotheses		Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Label	
Sustainable Business Performance	<---	Digital Exploitation Capabilities	,099	,050	1,993	,046	H1a
Market-Driven Business Model Innovation	<---	Digital Transformation	,037	,054	,701	,484	H4a
Sustainable Business Performance	<---	Digital Transformation	,225	,038	5,841	***	H4b
Customized Business Model Innovation	<---	Digital Transformation	,088	,047	1,881	,060	H4c
Sustainable Business Performance	<---	Market-Driven Business Model Innovation	,013	,043	,313	,754	H5
Sustainable Business Performance	<---	Customized Business Model Innovation	,213	,053	4,006	***	H6

*Indicates significant paths: *p < 0.05, **p < 0.01, ***p < 0.001. significant.

DISCUSSION

Over the past ten years, the digitalized business environment has encouraged various industries to embrace new opportunities in digitalization, resulting in enhanced sustainable business performance (Van Looy, 2021). Consequently, numerous sectors have adopted ambidextrous capabilities, leading to the establishment of a business management system designed to expedite sustainable outcomes (Agrawal et al., 2022). Nowadays, industries' vision, strategy, organizational structure, and competencies have been greatly impacted by the integration of renewable external and internal resources, which has improved their sustainable performance (Belhadi et al., 2022). This study identified that the dual aspects of exploitation and exploration in digital capabilities are critical drivers of sustainable performance.

The long-term sustainability perspective indicates that businesses must adopt digital capabilities that impact sustainable outputs (Gomes et al., 2020) and business innovation models. Exploitation capabilities have empowered industries to enhance performance through innovation (Hossain et al., 2023). Additionally, ambidextrous capabilities have allowed firms to adjust their operations to satisfy existing customer demands (He et al., 2021). Consistent with existing literature, the findings support hypotheses H1 and H2, concluding that the implementation of digital capabilities extends beyond merely designing industry assets to achieve sustainable outputs (Q. Li et al., 2021). Therefore, industries aiming to maintain their market position should focus on both exploiting and exploring innovation. The exploration perspective within industries serves as a vital catalyst for sustainability (Zhang et al., 2023). This strategy, which is a foundation of modern company dynamics, allows industries to innovate in a variety of fields, which eventually results in long-term commercial success (Yavuz et al., 2023). According to the results, exploitation and digital exploration skills are crucial for attaining long-term success, and market dynamics stimulate business model innovation.

Park and Mithas (Park & Mithas, 2020) identified that a digital strategy can enhance sustainable performance. Similarly, Proksch et al. (Proksch et al., 2024) asserted that a firm's strategy, rooted in digitalization, enables dynamic innovation to address existing customer demands. In line with these observations, this study determined that digital implementation is essential for influencing sustainable performance and business model innovation (BMI) driven by market dynamics. Furthermore, it was noted that digital transformation plays a significant role in enhancing sustainable business performance (Veckalne et al., 2022). This transformation also empowers industries to expand their BMI. By reconfiguring business models, digital transformation allows industries to optimize market potential, thereby contributing to sustainability (Costa Melo et al., 2023). In light of the recent remarkable growth in digitalization and the substantial rise in business technology, customer needs are increasingly being met through technological advancements (Piepponen et al., 2022). Consequently, this supports all hypotheses presented in Hypothesis 4.

Smart businesses have gathered insights from stakeholders to enhance sustainability (Gupta et al., 2023). As noted by (Amankwah-Amoah et al., 2021) market-driven business model innovation (BMI) serves as a significant catalyst for achieving sustainable performance. Market-enabled industries are prompted to establish functions that support long-term viability (Latilla et al., 2021). Research indicates that the digital capabilities associated with both exploitation and exploration have stimulated market-based BMI, which is recognized as an effective approach for attaining sustainable performance (Liao et al., 2020). This market-oriented BMI has facilitated the development of digital capabilities that promote sustainability. Furthermore, these capabilities have provided industries with access to valuable resources, thereby enhancing their sustainable performance (Abhari & McGuckin, 2023). The focus of these capabilities lies in service creation and design, contributing to market development. This demonstrates that market-leveraged BMI has increased the ambidexterity of industries' market orientation. As a result, these capabilities actively drive trends that affect sustainable performance in addition to offering insights into market dynamics. Furthermore, the results show that digital tactics significantly affect sustainability.

(Morgan & Anokhin, 2020) . Market-based innovation models have also contributed to sustainable performance (Mai et al., 2021), assisting industries in meeting the demands of potential customers. The results further reveal that in the realm of technology, digital transformation has led industries to prioritize the integration of innovation, allowing businesses to leverage customer experiences and thereby reap the benefits of sustainability. A new trend in information technology has emerged, highlighting the significance of digital leadership in facilitating digital transformation and promoting sustainable performance (Mahmood et al., 2023).

Research findings corroborate existing literature, indicating that a leader's vision regarding digital transformation enhances business model innovation (BMI) and sustainable performance (Benitez et al., 2022). Digital leadership (DL) is particularly adept at responding to market demands, with its focus on customer needs steering attention towards digitalization. The unique qualities of DL position leaders as primary motivators for sustainable performance, with

market-driven BMI playing a supportive role. Consequently, this research affirms the acceptance of the role of BMI. Overall, the study concludes that achieving sustainability as a business objective is bolstered by existing market changes that foster a supportive business environment. The essential takeaway is that staying ahead of the curve is vital, alongside recognizing the importance of innovative models and digital capabilities to attain sustainable business performance.

Study Limitation and Future Direction

Results from the research model explain how various digital aspects shaped digital leadership capability and sustainable business performance. Nevertheless, this research presents some limitations. In the first place, this study employs a relatively small sample size. Therefore, to enhance the relevancy, larger sample sizes can be used in future research. Secondly, this study exclusively focuses on a single industry. To provide cross-sectoral results, multi-industry studies can be done as the future research agenda for broader findings implications.

Thirdly, the investigation is limited to the proposed model, without other significant digital drivers outside this model. Following this fact, we encourage future researchers to broaden the scope of their empirical research by examining a greater variety of constructs, including organizational culture, customer satisfaction, employee IT skills, industry uncertainty, and eco-innovation processes, to improve our understanding of this subject. Importantly, we offer these recommendations as useful advice for upcoming researchers to deepen the analysis of the topic. Additionally, the paper suggests that companies investigate multifaceted digitization architectures that support long-term commercial success.

Theoretical Contribution

This study underlines the favorable effects of digital factor implementation. By examining the roles of organizational ambidexterity, digital strategy adoption, digital transformation, market-driven business model innovation, digital leadership capabilities, and long-term business performance, this study primarily fills in theoretical gaps or discrepancies in earlier research. Second, this study aims to update the body of current literature by doing modern research. Third, the study establishes a new paradigm by investigating the mediating function of market-driven business model innovation and the moderating influence of digital leadership competencies. By presenting a substantial body of literature on diverse digital concepts as key drivers of long-term corporate success, the main objective of this research is to highlight and close existing gaps in how digital elements and mechanisms drive global industries.

Furthermore, for a specific purpose, we hope that the findings will encourage global academics to explore the benefits and usefulness of these aspects in achieving long-term sustainable growth. This study improves individual understanding of the dynamic nature of technology and its impact on sustainable performance by giving useful insights into successful digitalization methods. Furthermore, this study emphasizes the need for new research models on this subject for future investigation. Hence, researchers are encouraged to delve deeper into the topic by conducting applicable investigations to nurture positive changes across industries.

Managerial Implications

This study has important implications for organizations, managers, policymakers, and practitioners. This report urges firms to use their resources to develop digital competencies to achieve performance sustainability. Ambidextrous capabilities effectively enhance organizational flexibility and support sustainable business performance. In today's rapidly evolving markets, managers are encouraged to prioritize developing ambidextrous capabilities (e.g., exploitation and exploration) and sustainable performance, concerning the positive relationship between these capabilities.

To resolve the sustainability dilemmas based on digitalization factors. The findings suggest radical integration and optimization of new strategies to meet customer demands and significantly improve sustainable corporate performance. The adoption of digital strategies focuses on business model innovation, with an emphasis on maximizing. To enhance long-term business success, authorities should ensure the digital strategies implementation is dedicated to identifying and capturing customer and market needs.

Furthermore, this study indicates how digital transformation expands the prospects that encourage long-term corporate success and market-driven business model innovation, as perceived by managers. As these drivers stimulate positive outcomes, managers are suggested to promote digital values, norms, and capabilities within their organizations. Including digital implementation training for the employees to meet customer needs effectively. The major goal is to educate employees about the importance of customer-centric organizational procedures. In general, investment in technology and personnel development is required to alter company activities and promote exponential long-term corporate performance.

Digital technology has fundamentally reshaped business operations and generated numerous advancements to accelerate corporate growth. However, amid the digitalized and complex corporate approaches, many organizations struggle to stay sustained in today's environment. Long-term sustainability requires deep innovation paradigms. Therefore, developing measurable skills, capabilities, and processes is an inevitable endeavor for companies to drive sustainable corporate performance. Aligned with dynamic capability theory, organizations should integrate, build, and reconfigure internal and external resources to achieve long-term success.

In order to achieve sustainable performance, this study examines the relationship between digital ambidextrous capabilities (such as digital exploitation and exploration), digital strategy adoption, and digital transformation. It also looks into the moderating role of digital leadership capabilities and the mediating role of market-driven business model innovation. The data show positive outcomes and validate all hypotheses. As a result, this study offers significant theoretical and practical insights, making it an invaluable tool for researchers, practitioners, organizations, and scholars.

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